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Automated High-Speed Approaches for the Extraction of Permanent Magnets from Hard Disk Drive Components for the Circular Economy.

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Abstract

This work describes an automated pilot plant for the extraction of rare earth (RE) permanent magnets from computer hard disk drives (HDDs), demonstrating a commercially viable way to exploit abundant sources of end-of-life (EOL) magnets. A mobile approach is provided for the on-site destruction of HDDs in server farms in compliance with the European Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), enabling the separation of the magnets and the automated shredding of the data carrier. The fully automated process identifies (optically and magnetically) the location of the rare earth magnets and cuts off the corner of the hard drive containing the rare earth material in the voice coil motor. This allows a significant reduction in magnet extraction time (6 seconds per HDD) compared to previously reported semi-automated (2 minutes) and manual (5 minutes) dismantling times.

The work will also help to transfer the experience gained in the mobile pilot plant to other future EOL material sources such as drive motors and mixed electronic scrap.

Keywords: Permanent Magnets, Rare earth (RE), NdFeB, Recycling, Circular Economy, Critical Materials, HPMS, Hydrogen Processing of Magnetic Scrap, Hydrogen Decrepitation, End-of-Life (EOL) Magnets, Hard Disk Drives (HDDs), Magnetic Scanner, Magnetic Image Analysis.

1. Introduction

Rare earths (RE) are used in permanent magnets, which are crucial to Europe's successful green and digital transition as they are essential components for electronics, communications and medical equipment, renewable energy, robotics, electric vehicles and aerospace. While the EU is a world leader in the production of electric motors, it is dependent on imports along the value chain for RE magnet materials. As a result, the REs neodymium, praseodymium, dysprosium and terbium have been identified as the most critical raw materials in Europe [1]. To unlock the commercial potential of the RE materials already in circulation, improved recycling technologies are needed [1].

The Hydrogen Processing of Magnetic Scrap (HPMS) route is a technologically and environmentally sound approach to extract and reprocess high performance RE permanent magnets for Europe's high-tech applications and green energy conversion [2, 3]. The economic success of magnet recycling depends less on the technical feasibility of the downstream recycling process itself, but the main cost driver is the extraction of the magnets from the respective components, often caused by poor design for recycling [4]. Using advanced technologies such as high-performance sensors, high throughput analysis and networked handling systems, this work demonstrates the feasibility of automated dismantling of geometrically diverse scrap sources at TRL 6-7, even if they are not specifically designed for easy extraction of the permanent magnets.

By integrating these secondary materials as valuable resources, the increasingly circular supply chains will ensure the availability of REs in Europe, reduce the EU's dependence on foreign monopolies and ultimately bring magnets to market at a cost advantage compared to magnets based on primary materials.

2. Data acquisition

As part of the preparatory work, more than 180 applications from various industries (e.g. waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE), industrial motors, generators, pumps, loudspeakers, sensors, household appliances and automotive components) were manually disassembled and tested for their magnetic content.

All data sets were stored in a database, part of which will be made openly available as part of the Horizon2020 project SUSMAGPRO [5]. Based on a tailored set of parameters [6], the most promising applications for recycling permanent magnets in a circular economy were selected for the development of automated disassembly processes. One such identified source of scrap is the voice coil magnet of computer hard disk drives: While HDDs have largely been replaced by Solid State Drives (SSDs) in consumer applications, the increasing number of server farms for cloud applications and centralised data storage is resulting in a significant number of HDDs that need to be destroyed on a regular basis to ensure reliable storage and data protection.

However, to ensure compliance with the requirements of the European Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [7], they are not included in the normal waste stream, but are destroyed on-site in specialised recycling facilities or in bespoke mobile shredding units.

Each HDD contains two RE magnets, a polymer-bonded magnet for the spindle motor that spins the disc and two sintered magnets for the voice coil that controls the read arm. As the spindle motor magnet is polymer bonded, recycling is complex and has a low yield. As it also contains little magnetic material due to its small size, this work focuses on extracting the commercially much more interesting voice coil magnet for further recycling using the HPMS process.

The aim of this work was to develop a fast, reliable and mobile process for extracting the magnets from the hard disk drive prior to shredding in order to make them available for commercially viable recycling. The fully automated process presented identifies and cuts off the corner of the HDD containing the voice coil magnet. This allows a significant reduction in magnet extraction time (6 seconds per HDD) compared to previously reported semi-automated [8] (2 minutes) and manual (5 minutes) dismantling times.

3. Development of an automated HDD processing line

3.1 Magnetic scanner system

To determine the position of the magnet inside a hard disk drive, a magnetic sensor array was constructed by mounting several 3-axis magnetometers in a row on a printed circuit board (PCB), Figure 1 (left). The magnetic field strength at the surface of a magnet containing scrap objects typically varies in a wide range of 0.01-100 mT. To cover such a wide range of magnetic fields, the sensor board was equipped with two parallel rows of two different types of magnetometers, one row of higher sensitivity/lower range 3-axis Anisotropic Magneto Resistance (AMR) sensors (Memsic MMC5983) and one row of lower sensitivity/higher range 3-axis Hall sensors (AKM AK09970N). The sensor-to-sensor spacing in each row was 5 mm and each PCB contained 24 AMR and 24 Hall sensors.

Fig. 1: Sensor PCB (left), schematic drawing of the digital interface controlling 3 magnetic sensor PCBs (right) which are placed underneath a conveyor belt (see also fig. 2).

The scanner was equipped with 3 sensor boards arranged side by side. The magnetic scanner thus had a total of 72 + 72 magnetometers and covered a total belt width of 335 mm. The sensor sampling rate was 80 Hz, which for a conveyor belt moving at 30 cm/s results in a spatial resolution of the magnetic image of 3.75 mm in the direction

of belt travel. The magnetic sensors were calibrated in a 3-axis Helmholtz coil prior to installation under the conveyor to determine the individual magnetic sensor gain and offset values.

The sensor arrays were controlled through digital communication from a PC to the on-board microcontrollers and the resulting measurement data were returned using Ethernet UDP communications. The sampled sensor data from the AMR and Hall sensors was merged into a single magnetic image, selecting data from the AMR sensors below a threshold magnetic field strength ($500 \mu\text{T}$) and from the Hall sensors above this limit. The magnetometer PCBs were mounted approximately 5 mm below a conveyor belt, with the sensor rows perpendicular to the direction of belt travel. The conveyor belt (Easy Systems Svenska AB) was 200 cm long and 60 cm wide and ran at an adjustable speed in the range of 0 to 50 cm/s. The magnetic sensor array in combination with the conveyor belt forms a magnetic scanner, able of generating sequential images of passing objects. The image is created by combining each line of recorded data as the object passes the magnetic sensor array.

Fig. 2. Magnetic scanner unit

The scanner unit (Fig. 2) was equipped with a camera (Basler aca2040-55UC) and a light dome (Advanced Illumination DL071) to provide illumination across the scanned objects and minimise light-scattering of uneven surfaces. An optical line detector (SICK HLG2) was used to detect an incoming object and trigger the measurement and object analysis routine. The trigger was also used to synchronise the scanner and the robot, which subsequently manipulates the object and positions it in a cutting operation.

The magnetic scanner control software was triggered when an object passes an optical line detector. A camera image was captured and analysed by the software (shape, position and rotation). The image and magnetic data were then combined to create a magneto-optical image (Fig. 3).

The image acquisition and analysis routine was written in Python using opencv, an open source image processing library [9]. The routine developed, subtracts the background of the image (the conveyor belt) to find the corners of the hard disk in the image. The coordinates of the 4 corners are saved onto the magnetic image for further analysis.

Figure 3. HDD without the top lid, the location of the magnets indicated in red (left), scanned magnetic field overlaid on the optical image (right)

The magnetic analysis routine was written in LabView. The routine takes the coordinates of the 4 corners and determines whether the shape and size are consistent with the dimensions of a 2.5" or 3.5" drive. The corners are mapped onto the magnetic image and the magnetic field within a circle around each corner is analysed to locate the voice coil corner (VCC).

Figure 4. HDD with identified magnet corner (red circle).

The radius of each analysis circle is set to half the distance between the shorter sides of the drive. The voice VCC is identified as the circle containing the largest standard deviation of the magnetic field (Fig. 4). For further processing, i.e. the extraction of the magnet-containing VCC from the HDD, the robotic arm receives a message about which corner to cut (see section 3.2), the results are displayed and stored for further processing, e.g. statistics or process control, etc.

The focus of the HDD algorithm development was to improve the speed of data analysis. The time to locate the HDD magnetic corner from the image and magnetic data analysis is less than 25 milliseconds. With a typical conveyor belt speed of 30cm/s, the HDD moves less than 10mm during corner analysis, making the routine fast enough to match the other processes involved in the HDD pilot.

3.2 Robotic arm with an HDD gripping tool

Following the scanning unit, a Fanuc M-10iA six-axis industrial robot (Fig. 5, left) is used together with a pneumatic gripper (Fig. 5, right) specifically designed to pick up HDDs from both sides, regardless of their size (2.5" or 3.5"). The gripper is capable of handling screws or any minor irregularities in the shape of the disks, but a pre-inspection of the HDDs is recommended to ensure that, for example, frames are removed before they are fed into the system. The robot receives a message via TCP/IP from the magnetic scanner about the type of object being scanned (2.5" HDD, 3.5" HDD or other), its position and rotation, and which corner to cut. Since the HDDs are moving on a conveyor belt, the position is given at the time the optical trigger line is broken. Knowing the speed of the conveyor belt, from a wheel encoder mounted on the belt, it is possible to calculate the position as a function of time. The robot picks up the hard drive and delivers the designated corner to the alligator shear cutter.

Figure 5: Fanuc M-10iA industrial robot (left) and tailored pneumatic gripping tool (right)

Figure 6: Robot placing the HDD in the cutter (left) and cutting process (right)

3.3 Alligator shear cutter

The robotic arm feeds the HDD, magnetic corner first, into the gap of an alligator shear cutter (Deltax DTX 310, fig. 6 left). The cutter is equipped with a clamping arm that holds the HDD in place before the shearing force is applied (fig. 6, right). The time it takes to clamp and cut a corner from an HDD is approximately 6 seconds, which is currently the bottleneck that limits the capacity of the HDD pilot.

After cutting, a pneumatic system ejects the remaining HDD and simultaneously cleans any residue left on the cutting base. The sheared off magnetic corners are collected in a container under the cutter for direct HPMS treatment without further processing or disassembly.

4. System integration and magnet extraction from HDDs

An automated pilot line for removing magnets from HDDs was built inside a 20ft container, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. HDD pilot built inside a 20ft container (left) and container with processed HDDs in front (right).

The setup consists of the components described above: magnetic scanner, robot with HDD gripper tool, alligator shear cutter and a shredder (to be installed). The workflow is illustrated in Figure 8. At the front end of the magnetic scanner is an input gate for HDD feed control. The gate closes when an HDD is detected by the optical trigger. The gate remains closed until the system is ready to process the next disc. This allows the operator to place the next disc on the belt without the risk of jamming the system.

The cut corner falls into a separate bin, while the rest of the disc is ejected onto a conveyor belt designed to feed the rest of the disc into a shredder for secure destruction of the stored data. The system is designed to be operated from outside the container for operator safety and is equipped with multiple emergency stops and a physical barrier with opening detection to stop the system immediately in the event of an emergency. A transparent guard has also been provided to prevent any part of the hard drive being projected outwards during the cutting process. The position of the belts and material discharge areas are designed to allow the resulting material to be discharged directly from the container through easily accessible openings.

Figure 8: Work-flow chart of the HDD NdFeB magnet harvesting pilot

To test the operation, reliability and throughput of the pilot line, 860 kg of discarded HDDs were processed under realistic operating conditions. The pallet (Figure 9, right) contained 605 3.5" HDDs and 2081 2.5" HDDs. Approximately 10% of the HDDs received had to be manually pre-processed as they were enclosed in various frames from the PC chassis assembly.

The system was managed by a single operator who fed the drives into the scanner and monitored the process. Tests proved reliable operation at a speed of 10 HDDs per minute, giving a capacity of 600 HDDs/h, with a power consumption of less than 7kW. As each HDD was scanned and analysed, the pilot line could handle a mixed input of 2.5" and 3.5" HDDs.

The weight of the two voice coil magnets inside each HDD varies considerably between different models [10, 11]. Assuming an average magnet mass of 12 g for 3.5" HDDs, the pilot capacity was approximately 7.2 kg NdFeB/h. Based on 260 working days and 8 hours per day, this equates to 15 tonnes of NdFeB per year from 1.25 million HDDs. As described above, the bottleneck in the pilot line was identified as the 6 second cycle time of the alligator shear. The magnetic scanner and robot have the capacity to run much faster, and cycle times down to 1 s per HDD appear feasible with a faster method of cutting the HDDs.

5. Discussion and Outlook

An automated pilot line for removing magnets from HDDs has been built inside a 20ft container. The line consists of a magnetic scanner, a robot with an HDD gripper, an alligator shear and a shredder (to be installed). Based on processing of 3.5" HDDs, the pilot capacity of 600 HDDs/hour produces ~7.2kg NdFeB/h, which equates to 15 tonnes of NdFeB per year from 1.25 million HDDs.

To put these figures into perspective, the EU imports 16,000 tonnes of NdFeB per year and domestic EU magnet production is approximately 1,000 tonnes of NdFeB [12]. A recent European Commission proposal for a regulation on critical raw materials [13] set a target that at least 15% of the EU's consumption of strategic raw materials should come from recycling, which would correspond to approximately 2,500 tonnes of NdFeB. The capacity of a single HDD pilot in its current form therefore represents approximately 0.6% of this target.

The current number of HDDs available for recycling in the EU is estimated to be in the region of 50 million HDDs per year [14]. This means that there is a potential to recycle approximately 500 tonnes of NdFeB from HDDs in Europe. This would require a processing capacity of about 30 HDD pilots in their current form (or 5 pilots assuming a fast-cutting method synchronised with the other equipment).

Estimates of the number of HDDs available in the future depend on several trends occurring simultaneously. The need for data storage capacity continues to grow, but HDD technology is being replaced by faster and more reliable SSD technology. However, HDD storage is still cheaper per TB than SSD, therefore HDDs are expected to have a viable future market in data centres. The collection rate of EOL hard drives in data centres is generally much better than for consumer electronics [15]. The requirements for secure data destruction in data centres mean that hard drives are more likely to be scrapped on site or sent to specialist recycling facilities. Having the HDD pilot in a container allows for easy transport between sites and makes it possible to provide secure on-site data destruction services.

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Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors certify that they have no affiliation or involvement with any organisation or entity with any financial interest (such as honoraria; educational grants; participation in speakers' bureaus; membership, employment, consultancies, stock ownership or other equity interest; and expert testimony or patent licensing arrangements) or non-financial interest (such as personal or professional relationships, affiliations, knowledge, or beliefs) in the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript.

References

- [1] European Commission, Critical materials for strategic technologies and sectors in the EU - a foresight study, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.2873/58081>
- [2] Sprecher, B., Xiao, Y., Walton, A., Speight, J., Harris, R., Kleijn, R., Visser, G., Kramer, G.; Life Cycle Inventory of the Production of Rare Earths and the Subsequent Production of NdFeB Rare Earth Permanent Magnets. *Environmental science & technology*. 2014 <https://doi.org/10.1021/es404596q>
- [3] Binnemans, K., Jones, P., Blanpain, B., Van Gerven, T., Yang, Y., Walton, A., Buchert, M.; Recycling of Rare Earths a Critical Review. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 2013 <https://doi.org/51.1-22.10.1016/j.jclepro.2012.12.037>.
- [4] Walton, A. Han, Y., Rowson, N., Speight, J., Mann, V. Sheridan, R., Bradshaw, R. Harris, I.R., Williams, A., The Use of Hydrogen to Separate and Recycle Neodymium-Iron-Boron-type Magnets from Electronic Waste; *Journal of Cleaner Production* 2015 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2015.05.033>
- [5] Jönsson, C., Awais, M., Pickering, L., Degri, M., Zhou, W., Bradshaw, A., Sheridan, R., Mann, V., Walton, A.; The extraction of NdFeB magnets from automotive scrap rotors using hydrogen. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 2020 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.124058>
- [6] Sustainable Recovery, Reprocessing and Reuse of Rare-Earth Magnets in a Circular Economy (SUSMAGPRO), <https://doi.org/10.3030/821114>
- [7] Burkhardt, C.; Lehmann, A., Podmiljsak, B. Kobe, S; A Systematic Classification and Labelling Approach to Support a Circular Economy Ecosystem for NdFeB-Type Magnet. *American Journal of Materials Science and Engineering* 2021 10. 125-133. <https://doi.org/10.17265/2161-6221/2020.7-8.001>.
- [8] General Data Protection Regulation, Art. 5, Principles relating to processing of personal data; <https://gdpr.eu/article-5-how-to-process-personal-data/>
- [9] OpenCV (Open Source Computer Vision Library). Open source computer vision and machine learning (AI) software library, <https://opencv.org>
- [10] Simon, TR.; Cong, L.; Zhai, Y.; Zhu, Y.; Zhao, F.; A semi-automatic system for efficient recovery of rare earth permanent magnets from hard disk drives. *Procedia CIRP* 2018 69. 916 – 920, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2017.11.024>
- [11] Dańczak, A.; Chojnacka, I.; Matuska, S.; Marcola, K.; Leśniewicz, A.; Wełna, M.; Żak, A.; Adamski, Z.; Rycerz, L.; The recycling-oriented material characterization of hard disk drives with special emphasis on NdFeB magnets. *Physicochem. Probl. Miner. Process.*, 54(2), 2018, 363-376, <https://doi.org/10.5277/ppmp1843>
- [12] Sprecher, B.; Kleijn, R.; Kramer, G.J.; Recycling Potential of Neodymium: The Case of Computer Hard Disk Drives. *Environmental Science & Technology* 2014 48 (16), 9506-9513, <https://doi.org/10.1021/es501572z>
- [13] Gauß, R.; Burkhardt, C.; Carencotte, F.; Gasparon, M.; Gutfleisch, O.; Higgins, I.; Karajić, M.; Klossek, A.; Mäkinen, M.; Schäfer, B.; Schindler, R.; Veluri, B.; Rare Earth Magnets and Motors: A European Call for Action. A report by the Rare Earth Magnets and Motors Cluster of the European Raw Materials Alliance. Berlin 2021, <https://erma.eu/european-call-for-action/>
- [14] European Union: European Commission, COM (2023) 160: Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL establishing a framework for ensuring a secure and sustainable supply of critical raw materials and amending Regulations (EU) 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, 2018/1724 and (EU) 2019/1020, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52023PC0160>
- [15] Reimer, M.V.; Schenk-Mathe, H.Y.; Hoffmann, M.F.; Elwert, T.; Recycling Decisions in 2020, 2030, and 2040—When Can Substantial NdFeB Extraction be Expected in the EU?. *Metals* 2018, 8(11), 867, <https://doi.org/10.3390/met8110867>